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Silicon photomultipliers for future HEP experiments

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ABSTRACT

For the particle identification systems of the future high-energy physics detectors, single-photon sensors with sub-mm granularity, high sensitivity, and mitigation strategy for operation in the neutron-irradiated areas are needed. Silicon photomultipliers are considered a baseline technology because of their high photon detection efficiency, good timing resolution, and low operating voltage compared to those of vacuum-based photo sensors. After neutron irradiation, the dark counts increase dramatically and distort the signal baseline, making the single photons indistinguishable. Although the DCR of different unirradiated SiPMs varies, the devices show very similar rates when irradiated to high doses. In this work, we investigated the performance parameters of FBK NUV-HD-RH UHD-DE 1 mm² devices and determined the working temperature. We show that the maximum operation temperature for samples irradiated with a fluence of 10¹² neq/cm² is around -100°C.

1. Introduction

For the LHCb Upgrade 2 [1], the expected fluence at the position of the RICH photodetector will be 3×10^{12} neq/cm², one of the highest in the currently foreseen RICH detectors. Also, a timing resolution for single photons below 100 ps σ is needed to associate photons to the tracks coming from different vertices. We studied the responses of FBK NUV-HD-RH UHD-DE 1 mm² SiPMs [2] at different temperatures and neutron fluences from 10⁹ to 10¹³ neq/cm² by measuring their temporal and amplitude responses to single photons.

2. Experimental setup

The short, low-light-level pulses emitted by an Alphaslas 20 ps laser were fed via a single-mode fiber to an RF-shielded box holding a SiPM sample, a custom cryogenic preamplifier board with μ PC2710 chip, and temperature sensors. The box was inserted in a cryogenic container filled with liquid nitrogen to cool the system. We used two heating resistors (100 Ω , 60 V) attached to the RF box, insulated with a 3D-printed ABS case and PE foam to conduct measurements at elevated temperatures in the range from -180 °C to -20 °C.

Three types of measurements were performed at different reverse bias voltages to characterize the samples: measurement of SiPM current, measurement of dark count rate without illumination, and acquisition of signal waveforms to single photons. The temperature control,

reverse biasing, and all subsequent measurements were fully automated and controlled using the National Instruments Lab Windows acquisition program. The signal from the pre-amplifier was first amplified using the Ortec FTA820 Fast Timing Amplifier and then split into two branches. The first one was fed in the CAMAC Philips Leading Edge discriminator and CAEN Scaler to measure a DCR, while the other was connected to the PSI DRS4 board triggered by a laser driver for waveform acquisition.

Six FBK NUV-HD-RH UHD-DE silicon photomultipliers of the size of 1×1 mm² with 15 μ m pixels, a gain of 5×10^5 electrons and a photon detection efficiency of 37% at 5 V overvoltage, recovery time constant of 6 ns and a quenching resistance of 450 k Ω have been characterized before and after irradiation in the triangular channel of the Jožef Stefan Institute 250 kW TRIGA nuclear reactor with neutron fluences from 10⁹ neq/cm² to 10¹³ neq/cm². After the exposure, all the samples were kept at a temperature of -20 °C.

3. Results

The integrated charge distributions for different temperatures are shown for a sample biased at 5 V overvoltage and irradiated to a 10¹² neq/cm² in Fig. 1. As we can see the single photon peak cannot be distinguished at -60 °C, while it can be resolved at -100 °C. The temperature, where the single photon peak can be seen, has also

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Fig. 1. Integrated charge distribution for a sample reverse biased with 5 V overvoltage and irradiated with 10^{12} neq/cm².

Fig. 2. Dark count rate as a function of a discriminator threshold for different neutron fluences at -100 °C and 5 V overvoltage.

been determined for other fluences and amounts to -20 °C, -60 °C, -100 °C, 140 °C, and -180 °C for samples irradiated at 10^9 neq/cm², 10^{10} neq/cm², 10^{11} neq/cm², 10^{12} neq/cm², and 10^{13} neq/cm² respectively.

The dark count rate as a function of a discriminator threshold is shown in Fig. 2 for samples biased at 5 V overvoltage and different fluences. Note, the steps in the functional dependence cannot be distinguished for a fluence of 10^{13} neq/cm² anymore.

The single photon timing resolution (SPTR) depends on the bias voltage of a device. The optimal SPTR of about 90 ps FWHM for this particular type of sensor was measured for unirradiated samples at 9 V overvoltage. It is clear that the operation at such a high overvoltage after irradiation is not possible due to the increased dark count rate and corresponding baseline distortion. We confirmed the timing resolution of irradiated sensors degrades with lowering the voltage, as expected for non-irradiated sensors. Hence, the operating voltage of irradiated sensors will also be worse. In Fig. 3, we plot the SPTR as a function of neutron fluence for different operating temperatures at 5 V overvoltage.

Fig. 3. Single-photon timing resolution at an overvoltage of 5 V as a function of fluence for different temperatures.

To meet the requirements of the LHCb RICH after Upgrade 2, the sensors biased at 5 V overvoltage will have to be cooled to below -100 °C for fluences up to 10^{12} neq/cm². As others have shown [3,4], annealing sensors might improve their operation. We annealed all the samples for 24 h at 80 °C, the maximum recommended temperature due to the conductive epoxy used to glue the SiPM dies to the interposer. Note that such an annealing temperature did not significantly change the samples' performance.

In summary, the operation of silicon photomultiplier after irradiation can be recovered by lowering the operation temperature. We showed that the sensor irradiated with 10^{12} neq/cm² can be used as a single photon detector by operating it at 5 V overvoltage at temperatures below -100 °C.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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